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To cite this article: Isaac M. Maitha, Michael W. Okoth, Lucy G. Njue & Duncan O. Mbuge (2025) Characterization of the attributes impacting industrial adoption of tree tomato fruit varieties in Kenya, Cogent Food & Agriculture, 11:1, 2464226, DOI: [10.1080/23311932.2025.2464226](https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2025.2464226)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2025.2464226>

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Published online: 16 Feb 2025.

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Characterization of the attributes impacting industrial adoption of tree tomato fruit varieties in Kenya

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ABSTRACT

Tree tomato (*Cyphomandra betacea*), is a nutrient-dense fruit but the physicochemical properties differ depending on the origin and cultivar. The study aimed at characterizing attributes impacting value addition and industrial adoption of tree tomato fruits varieties in Kenya. The red and yellow tree tomato fruit varieties were procured from Marigiti market in Nairobi, Kenya which is the main aggregation center and samples were randomly selected for characterization. Subjective color assessment was used to sort the fruits before randomly selecting samples for physicochemical characterization. The fruits had uniform, consistent geometric features which make them suitable for high-speed automated processes, suitable for selecting preparative unit operations to yield good quality end products. The color properties contribute to better understanding of the colorimetric aspects of tree tomatoes, which are important in selecting the best varieties of known processing performance, and best fruit pretreatments to help retain the natural color, value and quality of end products. The Chemical characterization results are important in designing and controlling the process to get high quality, nutritious and functional end products. The Kenyan red, compared to the yellow tree tomato had more promising functional properties, hence highly recommended as a valuable raw material for innovative food products.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 13 February 2024
Revised 2 August 2024
Accepted 3 February 2025

KEYWORDS

Tree tomato; characterization; cultivars; fruits; functional attributes

SUBJECT

Food Chemistry; Food Engineering; Agriculture & Environmental Sciences

Introduction

Fruits are generally perishable and seasonal agricultural products that require sustainable availability options while maintaining their nutritional properties. Fruits processing faces challenges in the availability of raw materials and demand for final products (Adeyeye, 2017). Most agro-industries cannot operate on a planned year-round basis due to inadequate, seasonal raw materials, which vary in quality characteristics and are unstable during storage (Atosina Akuriba et al., 2021).

Tree tomato, also called tamarillo, is a solanaceous fruit, scientifically known as *Cyphomandra betacea*, and has different varieties distinguished by their color ranging from Yellow, Black, Red, and Dark-red fruits. They are consumed garden-fresh by dividing it into two halves, then scooping together the pulp and the seeds (Diep, Rush, et al., 2020).

Tree tomato is a nutrient dense fruit mainly rich in minerals, fibre and vitamins, and if consumed regularly, it offers substantial health benefits (Diep, Rush, et al., 2020). It is an exceptional source of iron, vitamins A, B6, C, E and regular intake subsidize to meet the recommended daily intake (Kha et al., 2010). It has high content of pectin, and the pulp is rich in phytochemicals including phenolic, carotenoids and anthocyanin compounds (Diep, Rush, et al., 2020).

Their physicochemical properties differ depending on cultivar and where they are grown (Vasco et al., 2009). Characterization of the two available varieties in Kenya is key, to innovators who wish to utilize the fruit as a raw material for value addition, while preserving the functional properties.

The process suitability of tree tomato fruits as raw materials for industrial use should be determined by a balanced evaluation of their availability, geometric characteristics, mechanical properties, physicochemical

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characteristics, and functional properties (Pan et al., 2019). The availability of the fruits helps in predicting the prices and in production planning (Kartanaite et al., 2021).

Sampling, then testing of raw materials for conformity with processing requirements helps the processor carry out cost-effective operations (Muntean et al., 2022). The fruit geometry helps in designing or choosing suitable mechanized processes like washing, peeling and/or pulping (Kohli et al., 2021). Surface smoothness, size, and shape uniformity are key processing guides, which are useful during the sorting and grading operations of the fruits (Sravan & Tejaswini, 2020). These properties help in selecting the preparative operations, and processing conditions to yield good quality end product (Pan et al., 2019). The fruits surface properties, size, and weight, help in determining the yield and hence are important economic factors (Pan et al., 2019).

The maturity of the fruits is a key factor in controlling the manufacturing process and the final product quality (Liu et al., 2022). Flesh firmness which measures the force required for a probe to penetrate the fruit flesh to a given distance determines the fruit maturity. This is because in mature fruits the flesh softens due to hydrolysis of proto-pectin to the carbohydrate moiety and soluble pectin. Chemical constituents like sugar and acid change during maturity and their ratio consistency gives the fruits quality. The skin and flesh color helps in the selection of suitable varieties of known processing quality and in designing suitable pretreatment procedures to retain the natural fruit color (Pathare et al., 2013). It is important to carry out pilot analysis of the fruits physicochemical properties before processing to help in the selection of the best quality raw materials on a functional basis (Benchamas et al., 2020).

The study was aimed at characterizing the physicochemical attributes of the common tree tomato fruits varieties in Kenya, impacting their industrial adoption.

Materials and methods

Procurement of raw materials

About 500 kg of mature ripe tree tomato fruits were procured from five different traders at Marigiti market, Nairobi County in Kenya. The traders source their tree tomato from different regions of Kenya and are the major suppliers in the country. The fruits were pooled into either red or yellow batches and transported to the Department of Food Science,

Nutrition and Technology at the University of Nairobi. They were kept in a cold room at $7 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and 75% relative humidity (Huato- HE174 Data loggers Shenzhen China) before characterization and further processing.

Study design and sample preparation

This was an analytical study with experimental research involving laboratory analysis of the physicochemical properties of the fruits. Subjective color assessment was used to sort the fruits (Omayio et al., 2022a; Garcia et al., 2016) by randomly subdividing into four batches of 125 kg of each variety (red and yellow) (Omayio et al., 2022a). About 25 kg of each variety were randomly selected from each of the four batches (Pathare et al., 2013), and used to assess the physicochemical and functional properties and the rest were stored for further processing (Omayio et al., 2022a).

Methods of analysis

Fruits' physical characteristics

Fruit weights. A precision weighing balance AR3130 KERN® PCB 3500 (Balingen, Germany) was used to determine the fruit weights.

Diameter and length. A Mitutoyo digital vernier caliper (Japan) was used to measure the fruit's length and diameters.

Flesh firmness. The flesh firmness was determined using a fruit pressure tester (penetrometer), model FT.011, EFFEGI-48011 ALFONSINE-Italy, (0–11 Lbs), which measures the pressure necessary to force a plunger of specified size into the pulp of the fruit.

Twenty fruits of each variety were sampled, then half inch diameter disc of peel removed and measures taken on each fruit at the middle opposite sides. This was done as per the penetrometer manufacturer manual, by holding the fruit firmly in the left hand and the fruit tester held between thumb and forefinger of the right hand, then slowly pressed with increasing strength until the plunger tip penetrated into the pulp up to the notch, then pressure reading was taken.

Color. The skin and flesh color were taken using PCE (2014) colorimeter in accordance with the instructions provided by the manufacturer (PCE Instruments, London, UK). Calibration of the color meter was done against a standard calibration plate of a white surface and set to CIE Standard Illuminant C. The average values of 10 readings were taken as L^* , a^* , b^* .

The CIE L*a*b* scales were used to evaluate the color, where L* (brightness) 0=black and 100=white; a*(-) = green and (+) = red; b*(-) = blue and (+) = yellow.

The measurements were averaged, and total color difference (ΔE) estimated using Equation (1)

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(\Delta L^2) + (\Delta a^2) + (\Delta b^2)} \quad (1)$$

Yield. The fruit peels, seeds and pulp weights were determined by careful separation of the components and weighing. This was done in triplicate per 100 grams of each sample. Total mass was calculated using the Equation (2a). The solid (peels and seeds) and non-solids (pulp) components yield was determined using Equation (2b).

$$\text{Total mass(g)} = \text{Pulp(g)} + \text{Peels(g)} + \text{seeds(g)} \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{Pulpyield} = \frac{wp}{wt} \times 100 \quad (2b)$$

Where; wp is the weight of the pulp (g) and wt is the total mass (g).

Chemical characterization of the fruits

Proximate composition. The proximate composition of the tree tomato puree was determined according to AOAC (2010) test methods. Moisture content was performed according to test method 920:151; crude fibre was done as per test method 2011.25 while crude protein was determined according to test method 2001:11. Determination of crude fat was done according to test method 996.06 and ash content according to test method 940:26.

Carbohydrate content as a nitrogen-free extract (NFE) was performed using the difference as in Equation (3).

$$\text{NFE} = 100 - (\text{crude protein} + \text{crude fibre} + \text{moisture} + \text{ash} + \text{crude fat}) \quad (3)$$

Determination of energy content. The energy content was calculated by multiplying the carbohydrate, protein and fat contents by the Atwater's conversion factors, Equation (4):

$$\text{Energy(Kcal per100g)} = (4 \times \text{Carbohydrate}) + (4 \times \text{Protein}) + (9 \times \text{Fat}) \quad (4)$$

pH. A digital pH meter (Orion Research Inc., Cambridge, MA, USA) calibrated with buffer solutions of pH 4 and pH 7 was used to measure pH in accordance with ISO 26323:2009(en) standards. The pH meter electrodes were immersed in the samples

to obtain readings, and stable values were recorded.

Total soluble solids index (brix). ISO 2173:1978 method was used to determine the brix of the pulp. Total soluble solids index was measured in triplicate using a manual refractometer (SK106R.-SATO, Japan). The device was calibrated against distilled water and then, a drop of the extract at 20°C poured on to the prism and Brix index read.

Determination of total sugars. This was done as per the method described by Askar and Treptow (2017). About 25g of the fruit pulp was weighed and transferred to 250mL volumetric flask using about 100mL water. The mixture was neutralized with 1N NaOH, then topped up to volume and filtered through No.4 Whatman paper. 100mL aliquot was pipetted into a 500mL volumetric flask, 2mL of neutral lead acetate solution added and about 200mL of distilled water. The mixture was allowed to stand for 10min, then the excess lead was precipitated with potassium oxalate solution and topped up to mark then filtered to get the clarified solution. 50mL of the clarified solution was pipetted into a 250mL conical flask, and then 5g of citric acid and 50mL of water added. The mixture was boiled gently for 10min to completely invert the sucrose, and then cooled. After that it was transferred into a 250mL volumetric flask, neutralized with 1N NaOH using phenolphthalein as indicator and filled up to volume. 100mL aliquot was taken to determine the total sugar as invert sugars and calculated using Equation (5)

$$b = \frac{ca}{de} \quad (5)$$

Where: a = % Reducing sugar; b=mg of Invert sugar; c=Dilution; d=Titration; e=Wt of the sample.

Titrateable acidity. This was done according to AOAC (2010) Official test Method 942.15. The sample was prepared by mixing 1g with 10mL of distilled water (1% w/v), then analyzed in triplicates by titrating with standardized 0.1N NaOH to the end point. The titrateable acidity was calculated and expressed as percent citric acid, Equation (6):

$$\%TA = [10 \times V.NaOH \times 0.009 \times 0.1W] \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where; TA is Titrateable acidity; V.NaOH is Titre value; W is Weight of sample.

Determination of vitamin C. This was done according to AOAC (2010) Official test Method 967.21-1968 (2010) with slight modification. About

2 mL of the puree sample was titrated with 2, 6-dichlorophenolindophenol (DCPIP) solution until the end point. Vitamin C content of the tree tomato sample was calculated using Equation (7) and expressed as mg ascorbic acid per 100 g of sample:

$$\text{Ascorbic acid} = \frac{T.V \text{ of DCPIP} \times \text{DCPIP equiv} \times \text{Total volume of extract}}{\text{Volume of sample extract titrated} \times \text{Sample weight}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Vitamin A (retinol) determination. This was carried out as per the method described by Aremu and Nweze (2017). About 5 g of tree tomato sample was extracted using 25 cm³ of 95% ethanol, for about 20 minutes in a water bath at a temperature range of 60–80 °C. The extract was then cooled, decanted and volume (V1) measured. 85% ethanol solution was prepared, and then chilled for 5 minutes in ice water. A 12.5 cm³ quantity of petroleum ether was added to the cooled ethanol extract, then thoroughly mixed to homogenize the sample, then allowed to stand on a separating funnel to separate into two layers. Bottom layer was separated and returned into the funnel for further extraction using petroleum ether to obtain a fairly yellow extract. All the petroleum ether was collected and returned into the separating funnel for re-extraction using 25 cm³ of ethanol (85%). The clear layer from the final extract was measured and kept for more analysis. The extract's Absorbance was measured using a spectrophotometer (Hitachi 2900 UV/VIS spectrophotometer, Tokyo, Japan), at 436 nm wavelength, with a blank of petroleum ether. Each sample underwent five rounds of analysis and average figures were recorded. Concentration of $\hat{\alpha}$ -carotene vitamin A (Retinol) was calculated using formula (8):

$$1 \mu\text{g of Vitamin A (retinol)} = 6 \mu\text{g of } \hat{\alpha}\text{-carotene} \quad (8)$$

Phenolic content

Extraction. The extraction was done according to Asiimwe et al. (2022), but with few amendments. Two grams of powdered tree tomato was extracted by mixing it with 5 mL of extraction solution (20% distilled water: 80% methanol v/v). The mixture was put in a falcon tube and held for 20 minutes in ultrasonicator water bath set at room temperature. The extract was then cooled for 10 minutes at 4 °C before centrifuging at 0.011r (4000)²/9.81 = 17941r, (where r is the radius of the centrifuge in metres from the Centre to the tube holder) for 15 minutes. The supernatant was collected and stored at 4 °C in a refrigerator while

re-extraction of the residue was done as explained above. Both supernatants were put in a falcon tube, mixed and stored at 4 °C for total phenolic content (TPC) determination.

Determination of total phenolic content. This was done using Folin Ciocalteu colorimetric method (Arabshahi-Delouee & Urooj, 2007), with slight changes. For each extract, 100 μ L was pipetted into a test tube, then 0.25 mL of 0.2 N Folin–Ciocalteu reagent added, and covered using aluminium foil for 5 minutes. After that 1.25 mL of 7.5% (w/v) sodium carbonate was added then the mixture homogenized and allowed to change in color.

Absorbance was determined using a spectrophotometer (Hitachi 2900, UV/VIS spectrophotometer (Tokyo, Japan) at wavelength of 765 nm in a white background using 80% methanol as the blank. The results were determined using the standard gallic acid calibration curve and expressed as milligram gallic acid equivalent per 100 gram dry weight (mg GAE/100g DW).

Determination of flavonoid content. Using catechin as the reference, the total flavonoids were measured using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method (Omayio et al., 2022b). Stock solution (concentration of 100 μ g/mL), was prepared by dissolving catechin in methanol from which aliquots ranging from 0.1 to 1.0 mL were added to 10 mL volumetric flasks holding 4 mL of pure water and then 0.3 mL of sodium nitrite (5% w/v) was added. After five minutes, 0.3 mL of 10% w/v aluminum chloride and 2 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide were added and held for six minutes prior to adding distilled water to top off the volume to 10 mL capacity. A Hitachi 2900 UV/VIS spectrophotometer (Tokyo, Japan) was used to determine the absorbance at 510 nm in comparison to distilled water as a blank reagent.

A solution with a concentration of 1 mg/mL was obtained from the samples by dissolving 10 mg of each extract in 10 mL of methanol. Ten mL volumetric flasks containing four milliliters of distilled water were filled with an aliquot (1 mL) of each extract. After adding the matching reagents that were identical to the standards in the same way, 10 mL was obtained. The experiment was repeated twice and flavonoids content determined using the standard calibration curve and expressed in mgCE/100g DW (milligrams of catechin equivalents per 100 grams of dry weight).

Determination of antioxidant activity

Extraction procedure. The extraction was done as described in Phenolic extraction and then assayed

for antioxidant activity (DPPH radical scavenging activity).

DPPH radical scavenging activity determination. Hydrophilic antioxidant activity was analyzed using the 1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical method as described by Zacarías-García et al. (2021) About 2.9 mL of freshly prepared 80% methanol solution of 100 µM DPPH was added to 50 µL of tree tomato extract, then thoroughly mixed and incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature in a dark place. After that, the absorbance change of the mixture was determined in a UV/Vis microplate spectrophotometer (Hitachi 2900 UV/VIS (Tokyo, Japan) at 517 nm with 80% Methanol was used as the control. Each reaction was replicated thrice and a curve of Trolox solution with concentrations ranging from 25 to 200 µg mL⁻¹ used as the standard.

DPPH scavenging capacity was expressed as inhibition percentages by the formula (9) and results expressed as DPPH %/g DW.

$$\% \text{ radical scavenging activity} = \frac{Abs_{\text{control}} - Abs_{\text{sample}}}{Abs_{\text{sample}}} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

Where: Abs_{control}: Absorbance of the control;
Abs_{sample}: Absorbance of the sample.

Determination of mineral contents. This was ascertained using AOAC (2010) Official test Method 2005.08 for the contents of phosphorus (P), potassium (K), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), magnesium (Mg), copper (Cu), and zinc (Zn) using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model 210 VGP, Buck Scientific Instruments LLC, Fort Point, USA). Air oven drier (Memmert, Schutzzart DIN40050-IP20, West Germany) was used to dry approximately 5 grams of samples in three sets at 105 degrees Celsius until a steady weight was reached. Following the drying process, the samples were ground (Polymix® PX-MFC 90D, Kinematica AG, Switzerland) and the ash was digested in 36% HCL after being heated to 600°C in a furnace and filtered before the spectrophotometric reading done and the results were expressed as Milligrams per 100 grams of dry weight.

Data analysis

Data Analysis was done using R Software Version 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyse datasets and separation of means was performed using Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Results

Physical attributes of tree tomato fruits

The common tree tomato varieties in Kenya are the yellow and red types, distinguished by the distinctive red or yellow fruit skin color (Figures 1 and 2). Both varieties are either egg shaped or round in shape and with a smooth surface (Table 1).

The fully mature, ripe red variety, the flesh is yellow with red seeds, and the skin color is basically red (Figure 3), while for the yellow variety, the skin, pulp and seeds are basically yellow in color (Figure 4).

The average size, weight, and firmness of the fresh fruits were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) affected by the fruit variety (Table 2). The percentage yield per 100 grams (Table 2), of the pulp, and peels were not affected by the fruit variety ($p > 0.05$). The pulp to seeds ratio was higher ($p < 0.05$) in the red variety (4.00) than in the yellow variety (3.17) and both fruit varieties had significant amount of seeds inside the pericarp, as shown in the cross-sectional image (Figures 3 and 4).

Before peeling, significant ($p < 0.05$) color differences were found across the L*, b*, Chroma*, Hue angle* color parameters, with the yellow variety having higher values compared to the red variety (Table 3).

After peeling the fruits, the surface colors of the flesh was yellow and there was significant difference on the L* coordinates, with higher lightness (L*) value in the red variety as compared to the yellow variety ($p < 0.005$) (Table 4).

There were important differences between the proximate compositions of the red and the yellow tree tomato varieties (Table 5). The red variety had significantly ($p < 0.0001$) higher content of crude fat and total ash compared to the yellow variety. There was significant ($p < 0.0001$) difference in the crude protein content, the yellow variety had the highest compared to the red variety.

There was no significant difference between the pH values, total soluble solids (TSS), moisture and energy content of both varieties. The acidity level (citric acid) was significantly different ($p = 0.0001$), with the red variety having higher level compared to the yellow variety. The sugar acidity ratio was significantly different ($p = 0.018$), with a lower mean value for the red variety (Table 6). The minerals content (Table 7) of the yellow and red fresh varieties, was statistically different ($P < 0.05$) except for phosphorus.

Figure 1. Red Tree tomato varieties in Kenya.

Figure 2. Yellow Tree tomato varieties in Kenya.

The functional properties differed depending on the variety (Table 8). The phenols and flavonoids mean values were not statistically different ($p > 0.05$). The yellow variety was richer in vitamin A (retinol)

compared to the red variety but had a lower content of vitamin C. Antioxidant activity was significantly ($p < 0.0001$) higher in the red variety compared to the yellow variety (Table 8).

Table 1. Physical attributes of the tree tomato fruits.

Parameter	Red Variety	Yellow Variety	<i>p</i> -value
Weight (g)	59.80 ± 2.11 ^a	61.63 ± 2.56 ^a	0.583
Diameter (mm)	41.22 ± 0.75 ^a	40.77 ± 0.85 ^a	0.689
Length (mm)	60.03 ± 1.02 ^a	59.81 ± 1.10 ^a	0.885
Firmness (Lbs)	11.30 ± 0.16 ^a	11.52 ± 0.14 ^a	0.314
Shape	Egg shaped	Egg shaped	
	Round	Round	
Surface texture	Smooth	Smooth	
Peel color	Red	Yellow	
Flesh color	Yellow	Yellow	
Seeds color	Red	Yellow	

Values (means ± standard errors) with different superscripts across the row are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

Discussion

The Kenyan red and yellow tree tomato varieties did not differ in the average fruit weight, length and firmness. The average weight of both varieties was significantly smaller than of those from Ecuador (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020; Vasco et al., 2009). The average length of red and yellow tree tomato from Ecuador was (70-50mm) significantly greater than the Kenyan varieties (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The diameter of the red and yellow Kenyan varieties was

Figure 3. Cross-sectional view of the Red tree tomato varieties.

Figure 4. Cross-sectional view of the Yellow tree tomato varieties

higher than the varieties from Spain (46–39 mm (Liu et al., 2022)). The tree tomato varieties were classified as mature and ripe because they met length requirements of between 40–80 mm, diameter range of 35–60 mm and average weight range of 30–160 g (Acosta-Quezada et al., 2020; Acosta-Quezada et al., 2016). The weight and size are the major considerations for sorting, grading, and identifying visual consumer acceptance of the fruits (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The physical parameters are important in designing or improving the glitches on the available equipment and standardization of the processing procedures to address the gaps and improve the production efficiency (Liu et al., 2022). This will also reduce waste and create new economic opportunities by increasing returns and employment opportunities (Ramanathan et al., 2023). The uniform geometric features of the Kenyan tree tomato varieties' make them suitable for high-speed automated processing designs. The physical properties are fundamental in determining process suitability, appropriate for mechanized processes like washing and peeling.

There was significant ($p < 0.0001$) differences in the lightness (L^*) and yellowness (b^*) values between skin surface colors of the red and yellow tree tomato varieties. The higher lightness (L^*) and yellowness (b^*) values in the yellow variety than in the red variety, is a confirmation of the yellow variety which is distinguished by the bright yellow skin color. The skin surface color values from the present study, L^* (54.693, 50.522) for red and yellow varieties respectively, are similar to those reported by Viera et al.

Table 2. Yield per 100 grams of the tree tomato fruits and Yield Ratio.

Variety	Pulp yield	By-products		Yield Ratio (Pulp/By-products)
		Peels yield	Seeds yield	
Red fresh	82.34 ± 0.97 ^a	10.07 ± 0.61 ^a	7.59 ± 0.37 ^a	4.00 ± 0.43 ^a
Yellow fresh	83.20 ± 1.47 ^a	10.51 ± 1.22 ^a	6.30 ± 0.77 ^a	3.18 ± 0.00 ^b
Overall Mean	82.77	10.29	6.95	3.59
Range	6.16	2.96	3.2	1.4486
standard deviation	3.187	2.021	1.642	0.649
Coefficient of variation (%)	0.039	0.196	0.236	0.181
<i>p</i> -Value	0.6507	0.05	0.2039	0.018

Values (means ± standard errors) with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$).

(2022) who reported L^* value range of 33–77 in the two tree tomato varieties. Analysis of color parameters is indispensable because it provides information on the physical appearance of the fruit which is a quality attribute that determines consumer acceptance (Coyago-Cruz et al., 2023). The exocarp color is the best indicator for commercial fruit maturity, though it depends on the tree tomato variety (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The results obtained from the present study contribute to a better understanding of the colorimetric aspect of tree tomatoes, important during marketing and consumption of the fruits (Martin et al., 2021). Color changes of the fruits during postharvest handling and processing affect the value and quality of the end products (Pathare et al., 2013). The average pH of the tree tomato samples was 3.84 for the yellow variety and 3.90 for the red variety, which are, however, not significantly different. The results were consistent with the ones

Table 3. Color of tree tomato skin before peeling.

Chromacity coordinates	Variety Skin Color (Before Peeling)				
	L*	a*	b*	Chroma*	Hue angle*
Red Fresh	36.325 ± 2.682 ^a	16.210 ± 2.238 ^a	2.335 ± 1.184 ^a	16.634 ± 1.898 ^a	10.265 ± 6.588 ^b
Yellow Fresh	46.781 ± 4.324 ^b	18.809 ± 0.884 ^a	23.748 ± 7.262 ^b	31.924 ± 4.443 ^b	45.678 ± 13.157 ^a
ΔChromacity coordinate	-10.456	-2.5985	-21.413	-15.2903	-35.4133
ΔChromacity coordinate ²	109.3279	6.752202	458.5166	233.7917	1254.098
Δ E(Total color Difference)	23.97075				

Color values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Values with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$).

Table 4. Color of tree tomato surface after peeling.

Coordinates	Variety Surface (After Peeling)				
	L*	a*	b*	Chroma*	Hue angle*
Red Fresh	54.693 ± 0.929 ^a	10.973 ± 1.546 ^a	31.291 ± 0.493 ^a	33.309 ± 0.456 ^a	70.751 ± 2.680 ^a
Yellow Fresh	50.522 ± 1.205 ^b	13.210 ± 1.671 ^a	29.674 ± 1.305 ^a	32.609 ± 1.60 ^a	66.2506 ± 2.443 ^a
ΔChromacity coordinate	4.1706	-2.2366	1.6176	0.7	4.5004
ΔChromacity coordinate ²	17.3939	5.00238	2.61663	0.49	20.25360016
Δ E(Total color Difference)	5.001291				

Color values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Values with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$).

Table 5. Proximate composition of red and yellow tree tomato varieties.

Variety/ Attribute	%MoistureContent	%Protein	%Fat	%Fibre	%Ash	%Carbohy-drate	Energy (Kcal/100g)
Red fresh	88.89 ± 0.37 ^a	0.98 ± 0.02 ^b	0.09 ± 0.00 ^a	2.17 ± 0.00 ^a	1.41 ± 0.01 ^a	6.46 ± 0.46 ^a	30.57 ± 1.41 ^a
Yellow fresh	89.49 ± 0.10 ^a	1.70 ± 0.01 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^b	2.11 ± 0.01 ^b	1.04 ± 0.01 ^b	5.64 ± 0.12 ^a	29.54 ± 0.44 ^a
O.Mean	89.19	1.34	0.05	2.14	1.23	5.91	29.64
Range	1.23	0.77	0.08	0.09	0.39	1.49	4.83
Std. Dev.	0.53	0.39	0.04	0.04	0.2	0.54	1.64
C.V (%)	0.01	0.29	0.76	0.02	0.17	0.09	0.06
p-Value	0.196	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.006	<0.0001	0.245	0.777

Values (means ± standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$). The values were determined on a wet weight basis.

Table 6. Chemical attributes.

Attribute/ Variety	pH	Sugars (%)	TSS (%)	Acidity (%)	Sugar/Acidity Ratio
Red fresh	3.90 ± 0.02 ^a	3.51 ± 0.02 ^a	11.00 ± 0.29 ^a	1.89 ± 0.02 ^a	5.83 ± 0.18 ^b
Yellow fresh	3.84 ± 0.01 ^a	3.40 ± 0.02 ^b	11.33 ± 0.44 ^a	1.58 ± 0.00 ^b	7.16 ± 0.30 ^a
Overall Mean	3.87	3.45	11.17	1.73	6.50
Range	0.06	0.062	1.00	0.05	0.59
standard deviation	0.039	0.068	0.606	0.169	0.823
C. V (%)	0.010	0.020	0.054	0.097	0.127
p-Value	0.060	0.018	0.5614	0.0001	0.018

Values (means ± standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$).

Table 7. Minerals content (mg/kg F.W).

Variety/ Attribute	Phosphorus (mg/ kg F.W)	Potassium (mg/kg F.W)	Iron (mg/kg F.W)	Manganese (mg/ kg F.W)	Magnesium (mg/ kg F.W)	Copper (mg/kg F.W)	Zinc (mg/kg F.W)
Yellow fresh	2.05 ± 0.00 ^a	388.99 ± 3.62 ^b	36.53 ± 0.51 ^b	2.36 ± 0.19 ^a	274.20 ± 2.26 ^b	10.91 ± 0.72 ^b	12.28 ± 0.22 ^a
Red fresh	2.37 ± 0.00 ^a	481.19 ± 6.31 ^a	59.53 ± 1.59 ^a	1.43 ± 0.06 ^b	390.46 ± 2.01 ^a	15.83 ± 0.81 ^a	11.18 ± 0.30 ^b
Overall Mean	2.21	435.09	48.03	1.90	332.33	13.37	11.73
Range	0.322	110.626	26.704	1.236	121.175	7.425	2.022
Std Dev.	0.176	51.126	12.728	0.554	63.764	2.947	0.722
C.V (%)	0.080	0.118	0.265	0.292	0.192	0.220	0.062
p-Value	0.990	0.0002	0.0002	0.0094	<0.0001	0.0105	0.042

Values (means ± standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$).

reported from New Zealand (3.7–4.1) but higher compared to the pH range (3.2–3.6) for tamarillo sourced from Ecuador and Spain (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020; Wang & Zhu, 2020). There was also no significant difference between the TSS (Total soluble solids)

values for the red and the yellow fruit varieties. TSS mean range was from 11 to 11.33 °Brix and this agreed with the Vasco et al. (2009) report, of 10–11 and 11–12 °Brix for golden-yellow and purple-red tamarillos respectively but differs from the Diep,

Table 8. Bioactive compounds.

Variety/Attribute	Phenols (mg Gallic Acid equivalent/g)	Flavonoids (mg catechin (CAT) equivalent/g)	Antioxidant activity ($\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100\text{g FW}$)	Vitamin C (mg/100g)	Vitamin A (mcg RAE/100g)
Yellow fresh	24.44 \pm 0.58 ^a	3.38 \pm 0.33 ^a	1005.67 \pm 4.10 ^b	31.74 \pm 0.45 ^b	4.70 \pm 0.09 ^a
Red fresh	24.53 \pm 1.36 ^a	3.64 \pm 0.33 ^a	1660.33 \pm 4.63 ^a	34.89 \pm 0.30 ^a	2.75 \pm 0.05 ^b
Overall Mean	24.49	3.51	1331.50	33.31	3.73
Range	4.461	1.824	673.000	4.590	2.208
Standard deviation	1.622	0.706	360.283	1.822	1.079
CV. (%)	0.066	0.201	0.271	0.055	0.290
<i>p</i> -Value	0.957	0.706	<0.0001	0.0043	<0.0001

Values (means \pm standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$).

Pook, et al., 2020 report of 8.8 to 10.6 °Brix for Tamarrillo from New Zealand.

The red fruit variety had a higher titratable acidity than the yellow variety and that is an indication it is sourer in taste (García et al., 2016). The fruits' titratable acidity (citric acid) for the red (1.89%) and yellow variety (1.58%) was consistent with that reported from Spain but higher compared to that from Ecuador (2.7–2.5%), (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The yellow tree tomato variety had a higher Sugar/acidity Ratio than the red variety and that signifies the yellow fruits have better organoleptic properties (Brier and Lia Dwi Jayanti 2020). The Sugar/Acidity Ratio was 5.83–7.16 and the results were within the range for a minimum maturity index of 4.5 (Sugar/acid ratio), from other authors results (Viera et al., 2022). Though variances of sugar/acid ratio occur, they are attributed to the level of fruit maturity. There is usually increase in soluble solids, which is an indicator of maturity, and accumulation of organic acids that happens during ripening, but are spent after harvest due to respiration of the fruit (Zhang et al., 2021). The yellow variety in the present study had higher protein content compared to the red variety. The protein content of the Kenyan tree tomatoes differed from that from Ecuador (2.2–2.4%) and Spain (2.2–2.5%), however they were comparable to (1.8–1.9%) reported from New Zealand (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The fat content of the red and yellow Kenyan tree tomato varieties differed from that from Ecuador (0.6–0.72%) but were consistent with that from Spain (0.05–0.08%) (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The ash content of the red and yellow Kenyan tree tomato was higher than that of Ecuador (0.9–0.8%) and Spain (0.7–0.7%) (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The ash reflects mineral content therefore the higher levels can be linked to higher amounts of minerals and key micro-nutrients present in the samples (Coyago-Cruz et al., 2023). The chemical compositions are important as they help in determining the most suitable methods to be used during new products development and processing (Brier and Lia Dwi Jayanti 2020).

The Kenyan tree tomato vitamin C contents agree with the study by Coyago-Cruz et al. (2023) that found a range of 0.7 to 48.6 mg/100g DW. Total polyphenols found in the present study for the red and yellow varieties differed from those reported in New Zealand's varieties (8.75–7.07 mg GAE g⁻¹), and Ecuador (2.4 to 6.2 mg GAE 100g⁻¹) (Viera et al., 2022). The total polyphenols and the flavonoids contents of the red and the yellow Kenyan tree tomato fruit varieties were not significantly different. Regarding the Flavonoid compounds, the red and yellow Kenyan tree tomato varieties had higher mean average of 3.38–3.64 (mg cat g⁻¹ DW) compared to that reported from New Zealand (2.60–3.36 mg cat g⁻¹ DW); however, it was lower (6.44 mg cat g⁻¹) than that reported for Malaysian variety (Viera et al., 2022). The fruits can therefore act as an excellent source of flavonoids, which are known for the deterrence and remedy of diseases associated with free radicals (Viera et al., 2022).

The red Kenyan tree tomato fruit had a higher antioxidant activity than the yellow variety. The Antioxidant activity of the red and yellow Kenyan cultivars in the present study (1005.67–1660.33 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100\text{g FW}$) was consistent with that reported from New Zealand (1002–1659 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100\text{g FW}$) by Vasco et al. (2009). The yellow Kenyan tree tomato fruit had higher vitamin A content than the red variety and this is due to presence of beta-carotene pigment which gives yellow fruits their rich hues (Cömert et al., 2020). In the body, beta-carotene converts into vitamin A (retinol). We need vitamin A for good vision and eye health, for a strong immune system, and for healthy skin and mucous membranes.

The red and yellow Kenyan tree tomato cultivars in the present study were found to be rich in minerals, notably phosphorus, potassium, iron, manganese, magnesium, copper and zinc, and the values were higher than those reported for New Zealand Tree tomato varieties (Vasco et al., 2009). The phosphorus contents of the pulp of the red and yellow Kenyan tree tomato varieties were not significantly different. The red variety had higher contents of potassium,

iron, magnesium and copper than the yellow variety while the yellow variety had higher contents of manganese and zinc than the red variety. Potassium content in the Kenyan red (481.19 mg/kg F.W) and yellow (388.99 mg/kg F.W) tree tomato varieties in the present study was consistent with that from New Zealand 321–495 and 292–450 mg/100 g FW, that from Ecuador was 379 and 398 mg/100 g FW, respectively, whereas the Malaysian tamarillo contained a mean level of 410 mg/100 g (Diep, Pook, et al., 2020). The fruit can therefore be a good source of potassium, which is important for proper functioning of the nervous system cells (Jomova et al., 2022). Kenyan tree tomato is also an excellent source of essential minerals, required for biological processes in the body like copper which is required for the human body to use iron as intended, and also magnesium whose higher intake has been shown to improve elderly people's insulin response and glucose tolerance (Diep, Rush, et al., 2020).

The red variety was had better nutritional qualities than the yellow variety due to the high antioxidant activity, Vitamin C content and minerals (iron, magnesium and copper) content. The present study on the physicochemical attributes of Kenyan Tree tomato fruit varieties is important in identifying the common varieties in the Kenyan market and in developing local industrial centers to encourage the tree tomato supply chain. The observed differences between the present study's characterization results and those from published work in other countries could have been caused by seasonal, climatic, and regional differences and also the different cultivars (Diep, et al., 2020). The findings can be utilized to come up with specific process and unique products of Kenyan tree tomato based on the quality traits (Viera et al., 2022).

The present study on the attributes of Kenyan Tree tomato fruit varieties is important for identifying the common varieties in the Kenyan market and for developing local industrial centers to encourage the tree tomato supply chain (Liu et al., 2022). The Chemical compositions analyzed are important, as they will help in choosing the most suitable methods to be used during new product development and processing to preserve the nutrients (Brier & Lia Dwi Jayanti 2020). The red variety exhibited superior nutritional qualities than the yellow variety because of its high antioxidant activity, Vitamin C content, and minerals content making it more suitable for processing of nutrient dense food products or ingredients. These findings can be utilized to develop specific processes and unique products from Kenyan tree tomatoes based on the quality traits (Viera et al., 2022).

Conclusions and recommendations

The results obtained from this study clearly demonstrate the suitability of the underutilized, excellent nutrient dense Kenyan tree tomato for industrial application. The red variety which has excellent quality attributes can be used as a valuable raw material in food manufacturing for development of natural food ingredients, new products development especially the utilization of the fruit as a nutraceutical in innovative food products. The findings can be used in process engineering to develop unique products from Kenyan red tree tomato varieties. More studies to characterize browning color changes after pulping the fruit should be done to precisely assess the quality changes that can occur during processing operations.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the FoodLAND project for partnering with University of Nairobi and funding the research; also, the staff at the University of Nairobi's Department of Food Science, Nutrition, and Technology are thanked for technical assistance.

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Conceptualization: I. Maitha, M. Okoth, L. Njue, D. Mbuge; **Methodology and data analysis:** I. Maitha M. Okoth, L. Njue, D. Mbuge; **Writing-original draft preparation:** I. Maitha, M. Okoth, L. Njue, D. Mbuge, **Writing-review and editing:** I. Maitha, M. Okoth, L. Njue, D. Mbuge; **Supervision:** M. Okoth, L. Njue, D. Mbuge; **Project administration and funding acquisition:** M. Okoth. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

University of Nairobi, Kenya was one of the Research partners in the FoodLAND project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement (GA No. 862802).

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Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [Maitha, I. M.] upon request.

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